

Effect of Addition of Micro-Sized Silicon Nitride on the Thermal Properties of the Epoxy Composites

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Abstract:- In the present investigation, the effect of the addition of silicon nitride particulates in the epoxy resin is investigated and presented. The main concentration of the work is on the thermal properties of the developed material. The properties under investigation are thermal conductivity, glass transition temperature and coefficient of thermal expansion. All the properties are determined as a function of filler loading. The effect of modification of the surface of the silicon nitride using a silane coupling agent on the mentioned properties of the composites is also investigated. Four sets of composite specimens with filler content ranging up to 40 wt. % has been fabricated using a simple hand lay-up technique. From the experimental results, it is found that the inclusion of silicon nitride in the epoxy resin increases the thermal conductivity and glass transition temperature of the composite body as a function of filler loading. While studying the coefficient of thermal expansion, it is observed that the inclusion of filler gainfully decreases the coefficient of thermal expansion of the composite. It is also observed that the composite prepared with silane-modified silicon nitride shows better thermal properties as compared to its counterpart for a given filler loading due to the improvement in adhesion between the two phases.

Keywords—Epoxy, Silicon nitride, Thermal conductivity, Coefficient of thermal expansion, Glass transition temperature

I. Introduction

Nowadays, composite materials are everywhere as they extend their horizons in almost every branch of engineering and science. Polymer matrix composites (PMCs) are the best-established form of advanced composite materials. Of the two classes of polymers used as matrices, thermosets and thermoplastics, thermosets dominate the market for structural applications. Current research is being conducted on composite materials for thermoset as a matrix material. In the present work, epoxy is selected as a matrix material and a ceramic material i.e. silicon nitride is used as a filler material. Silicon nitride has been used for the development of composite material with polymer as a base matrix material in the past.

The usages of silicon nitride as filler material were mainly established in the twentieth century when He et al. [1] used this filler with a polystyrene matrix. They studied the thermal and dielectric properties of the developed material and reported achieving a thermal conductivity of 3.0 W/m-K with 40 vol. % of filler material. An et al. [2] incorporated silicon nitride with linear low-density polyethylene and studied the mechanical, thermal and electrical properties of the developed material. On a similar note, Ramdini et al. [3] used the same filler as nano-filler with polybenzoxazine matrix and fabricated the composites by compression moulding technique. They performed the DMA analysis of the samples and noticed improvement in stiffness and glass transition temperature of the developed material. Later in other work, Ramdini et al. [4] performed thermal conductivity measurement with increased filler content up to 70 % and reported achieving 5.78 W/m-K of conductivity value over 0.18 W/m-K against neat polymer. Kumar and

Reddy [5] worked on evaluating the mechanical and tribological properties of silicon nitride-filled Nylon-6 polymer composites. In their analysis, they found that incorporation of filler in small amounts increases the tensile strength but when filler content increases further, tensile strength decreases. Maximum value of tensile strength is obtained with 4 wt. % filler content. The hardness of the composite also increases with filler content up to 16 wt. %. With a further increase in filler content, hardness shows a decreasing trend. Wang et al. [6] developed high strength polymer composite with silicon nitride as filler for dental application. The developed material possessed excellent flexural strength with improved hardness and elastic modulus. Chen et al. [7] used silicon nitride with a polyamide matrix and studied the dielectric properties of the material.

Zgalat-Lozynskyy et al. [8] explore the utilization of silicon nitride particles as reinforcement in polymer materials for 3D printing. The research provides significant insights into enhancing the properties of 3D-printed polymer materials. Petousis et al. [9] present a comprehensive exploration of nanomaterials, focusing on optimizing the rheological and thermomechanical response of Acrylonitrile Butadiene Styrene (ABS)/Silicon Nitride nanocomposites for Material Extrusion Additive Manufacturing (MEAM). The study delivers significant findings, showcasing enhanced material properties. Wan et al. [10] explore the enhancement of in-plane thermal conductivity and mechanical strength in flexible films through the alignment and interconnection of Si₃N₄ nanowires. The study presents a noteworthy improvement in thermal conductivity, with the aligned and interconnected Si₃N₄ nanowires resulting in an impressive value of 3.27 W/m-K. Additionally, the mechanical strength

of the films is significantly improved, demonstrating a remarkable increase in tensile strength by 43% and Young's modulus by 31%. It is observed from the earlier investigation that the silicon nitride has been used with various matrix materials but its combination with epoxy resin is rare. Further, it is observed that the properties investigated are mainly thermal properties.

Against this background, in the present work, a class of composite is fabricated in which the continuous phase is a thermoset epoxy matrix and the discontinuous phase is micro-size silicon nitride particles. A simple hand lay-up method is used for the fabrication of composites with a wide range of filler content. The properties evaluated are thermal conductivity, glass transition temperature and coefficient of thermal expansion. Further, the effect of surface modification of the filler on the mentioned properties of the composites is also investigated and presented

II. Materials And Methods

A. Material used

Thermoset resin Lapox C-51 along with the hardener K6 is used as a matrix material in the present investigation. The matrix material system selected is supplied by ATUL India Ltd., Gujarat, India. Silicon nitride of size 50 microns is used in the present investigation supplied by Intelligent Materials Private Limited, Mohali. The surface of the silicon nitride is modified using a silane coupling agent and ethanol to study the effect of surface modification on the different properties under investigation.

B. Composite Fabrication

A simple hand lay-up technique is used in the present investigation for the fabrication of silicon nitride particles in an epoxy matrix. Two different sets of composites are fabricated. In set A, the composites are prepared with the addition of untreated silicon nitride particulates. In set B, the composites are prepared with treated silicon nitride composites. The treatment of the filler material and the fabrication of the composite body are by the previous work conducted by Agrawal and Chandrakar [11]. Table 1 shows the different composites prepared in the present investigation.

TABLE I: Epoxy composites filled with silicon nitride

SET A		SET B	
Set	Composition	Set	Composition
Set A1	Epoxy + 10 wt. % of untreated Silicon Nitride	Set B1	Epoxy + 10 wt. % of treated Silicon Nitride
Set A2	Epoxy + 20 wt. % of untreated Silicon Nitride	Set B2	Epoxy + 20 wt. % of treated Silicon Nitride
Set A3	Epoxy + 30 wt. % of untreated Silicon Nitride	Set B3	Epoxy + 30 wt. % of treated Silicon Nitride
Set A4	Epoxy + 40 wt. % of untreated Silicon Nitride	Set B4	Epoxy + 40 wt. % of treated Silicon Nitride

C. Thermal Characterization

The thermal conductivity of the composite materials is measured by the Unitherm Model 2022. The tests are conducted as per ASTM E-1530 Standard. In the present work, the glass transition temperature and coefficient of thermal expansion of the composites are measured with a Perkin Elmer DSC-7 Thermal Mechanical Analyzer.

III. Results And Discussion

A. Thermal Conductivity

The thermal conductivity value of the epoxy matrix and its micro-composites at various levels of silicon nitride loading are shown in Figure 1. The epoxy used in the present work has a very low thermal conductivity of 0.317 W/m-K and by adding the micro-size silicon nitride particulates, the thermal conductivity increases with increasing silicon nitride content. By addition of 20 wt. % of silicon nitride, the conductivity of composites increases to 0.512 W/m-K giving an increment of 61.5 %. It is further notified that when filler content increases beyond 20 wt. %, a sudden rise in the value of thermal conductivity is obtained. Here the thermal conductivity reaches 1.235 W/m-K and 1.412 W/m-K with filler content of 30 wt. % and 40 wt. % respectively. This is an increment corresponding to 289 % and 345 % respectively.

A similar trend is seen when the silane-modified silicon nitride is used. The conductivity of 0.492 W/m-K and 0.734 W/m-K is achieved for a silane-modified silicon nitride of 10 wt. % and 20 wt.%. For a filler loading of 40 wt. % silane-treated silicon nitride, the value of thermal conductivity reaches 1.723 W/m-K showing an improvement of 443 %. It is observed that the treatment of filler results in an improved heat conduction rate of composites for a given filler loading. It is mainly because of the improvement in the dispersion and adhesion of fillers in and within the matrix and the establishment of good bonding between the two phases.

Fig. 1 Thermal conductivity of epoxy filled with silicon nitride

B. Glass Transition Temperature

The glass transition temperature of epoxy composites filled with silicon nitride as a function of silicon nitride

content is shown in Figure 2. From the figure, it is clear that the glass transition temperatures of epoxy composites were higher as compared to that of neat epoxy and it increases with an increase in silicon nitride content. Glass transition temperature increases from 81.5 °C for neat epoxy to 88.4 °C for 40 wt. % untreated silicon nitride-filled epoxy composites. The increment is measured to be 8.4 % which is an appreciable improvement over neat epoxy. The increment was further improved when the treated silicon nitride fillers were added to the epoxy resin. For the inclusion of 40 wt. % of silane-treated silicon nitride. The glass transition temperature increases to 90.3 °C showing an appreciable improvement of 10.8 %.

An increase in glass transition temperature with an increase in filler content is mainly due to decrement in free volume which is otherwise present in the polymer matrix. This decrement in free volume restricts the mobility of the polymer chain which increases the glass transition temperature. The treated filler results in more improvement because the silane-modified filler possesses a better affinity for the matrix than the unmodified filler. This improves the interfacial interaction between the two phases and reduces the free volume of the polymer chain further.

Fig. 2 Glass transition temperature of epoxy filled with silicon nitride

C. Coefficient of Thermal Expansion

The inclusion of silicon provided is beneficial as with the increase in the content of silicon nitride, the CTE of the epoxy matrix decreases. The same can be seen in Figure 3. It is expected because the intrinsic CTE of silicon nitride is much lower than that of epoxy matrix. The CTE of the composite reduces from $63.5 \times 10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $54.6 \times 10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 40 wt. % of silicon nitrides. The decrement in CTE observed for the present combination is 14.1 %. The decrement is further modified when the treated fillers are used. For the similar loading of silane-treated silicon nitride, the CTE reduces to $51.3 \times 10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$ showing a decrement of 19.2 %. The network structure formed between the two phases by the silane modification of silicon nitride filler tightens the polyester chain at elevated temperatures resulting in the reduction in the expansion of the polymer chain.

Fig. 3 Coefficient of thermal expansion of epoxy filled with silicon nitride

IV. Conclusions

This experimental investigation has led to the following specific conclusions:

1. The epoxy has a very low thermal conductivity and by adding the micro-size silicon nitride particulates, the thermal conductivity increases. With the inclusion of 40 wt. % of untreated silicon nitride the maximum thermal conductivity reaches 1.412 W/m-K with the inclusion of 40 wt. % of silane-treated silicon nitride, the maximum thermal conductivity reaches 1.723 W/m-K.
2. Glass transition temperature increased from 79.8 °C for neat epoxy to 88.4 °C for 40 wt. % silicon nitride-filled epoxy composites. When a similar loading of silane-treated silicon nitride is added to the epoxy matrix, the glass transition temperature increases to 90.3 °C.
3. results in a reduction in the value of CTE. The CTE of the composite reduces from $63.5 \times 10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $54.6 \times 10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 40 wt. % of untreated silicon nitride. When 40 wt. % of silane-modified silicon nitride fillers are added, the CTE The addition of silicon nitride particles into epoxy of the composite reduces to $51.3 \times 10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$.

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